

Manual LAS Classification: Reclassifying LIDAR Points by Freehand Selection on an Active Classification

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Keywords:

LAS Classification, LIDAR, manual classification, GIS, software, algorithms;

In GIS and related fields, ensuring the accuracy of LiDAR data is crucial for further analysis and processing. To achieve the best terrain representation, users often need to adjust their datasets to fit specific requirements or types of analysis. This might involve isolating building points or distinguishing vegetation (such as high vegetation) from other objects like buildings.

Manual reclassification becomes essential when automatic classification algorithms struggle to differentiate between similar features—like vegetation and low-lying structures. While automatic classification is a highly valuable tool, it can sometimes falter in complex or heterogeneous landscapes.

In these situations, the ability to manually reclassify points provides users with greater control over their data, allowing them to refine it as needed for better accuracy. This makes freehand LAS classification an indispensable feature for professionals who require high-quality, precise spatial data.

With SGIS v.R, users can easily draw freehand polygons on the graphics panel to select specific points. Once selected, the LiDAR toolbox can then be used to reclassify those points into a different category. Let's walk through an example to see how this feature works.

Fig.1 Data loaded into SGIS v.R.

We've added a LAS point cloud, which contains classifications ranging from 1 to 7. For this example, we'll focus on points representing a solar farm. Due to an error in the automatic classification, these solar farm points were mistakenly classified as building points. To correct this, we need to reclassify the building points from class 6 to class 1, which designates them as Unclassified points.

Fig. 2 LAS point cloud loaded into SGIS v.R, showing classifications 1 to 7. The points highlighted represent a solar farm, which will be reclassified due to an incorrect initial classification.

Fig. 3 By disabling the ground points and adding a basemap, it becomes evident that these building points have been misclassified and require reclassification.

We've added a basemap to verify our observations. Now, let's uncheck both the basemap and the ground points. We've also switched the background color from light to dark because a black background makes it easier to view and manage the

points. Next, we need to check the point cloud layer and go to the Element Data panel to find the 'Active Classification' dropdown. From there, we'll select 'Buildings'.

Fig. 4 Navigating to the point cloud layer in the Layers Panel, then accessing the Element Data panel to choose 'Buildings' from the 'Active Classification' dropdown list.

Next, we need to activate the 'Polygon Selection' function so we can draw a polygon on the Graphics panel. On the right side, the 'Active Classification' is set to 'Building'.

Fig. 5 Activating the 'Polygon Selection' function to draw a polygon on the Graphics panel, with the 'Active Classification' set to 'Building'. The selected points will be highlighted once the polygon is drawn

Once the polygon is drawn, the selected points will be instantly highlighted on the graphics panel.

Fig. 6 Opening the 'LiDAR' toolbox and selecting class 1 (Unclassified) as the target for the selected points, followed by clicking the 'Set Up' button to confirm the reclassification.

We will open the 'LiDAR' toolbox. In this section, we need to select the class where we want to move the chosen points. In our case, that's class Unclassified or class 1. After that, we'll click the 'Set Up' button. The points will be reclassified and moved to class 1, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7 The points have been successfully reclassified and moved to class 1 (Unclassified), as indicated in the updated display.

Next, we'll enable all the existing classifications in the point cloud and click 'Apply.' Once the changes are applied, we can close the 'LiDAR' toolbox, as everything has been saved.

Fig. 8 Enabling all existing classifications in the point cloud and clicking 'Apply' to finalize the changes before closing the 'LiDAR' toolbox.

Fig.9 The procedure is complete.

With this, the procedure is complete.